

PEER- REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)
ISSN 2278-5655

Bi-Monthly

VOL - II

ISSUES - V

[2013]

Chief-Editor:

Ubale Amol Baban

[**Editorial/Head Office:** 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near TV Towar,Badlapur, MS

TRANSLATION: NATURE AND APPLICATION

Mr. Prakash Ganpat Kumbhar

Assistant Professor,

Department of English,

M.H Shinde Mahavidyalaya, Tisangi, Tal. Gaganbavadan, Kolhapur

Abstract

Translation is an art of certain knowledge describing, a certain education and a significant amount of talent are necessary. "In view of all these parameters, translators are underrated, underpaid and their place in society is a much nuanced one. They earn scant credit from readers and reviewers as well, and virtually no publicity. Translators are undervalued nowadays; their job is viewed as unimaginative and secondary. It is only necessary to research creativity if the translations are to a certain degree imaginative, but the creativity of translations relies on that of the source material. The translation is as ancient as the culture of man. We, human beings, have been using words to translate our emotions and concepts since the beginning of civilisation. Translation helps multiple cultures to interact, collaborate, and enhance each other." The primary aim of this essay is to explain how translation happens and plays a critical function in the world. Hence this paper brief discussion about the translation and its nature and application in modern age.

INTRODUCTION

The translation of the English term was originated from the translation of the Latin word, which itself came together from trans and latum, meaning 'a carrying across' or 'a taking across.' In other terms, it is the business of communicating from one document to another, from one person to another and from one language (source language) to another language over a message/written material (target language). Translation is a detailed form of the target language (TL) of the interpretation of a document in the source language (SL) without allowing the original message to be lost. If one is bilingual, it is sometimes assumed that he/she will be a successful interpreter, which is not the reality. People with strong listening and writing experiences will be good translators in both languages, which means being bilingual. A translator finds the essence of a text behind the forms in the source language (SL) when interpreting, and reproduces the same

meaning with the forms and mechanisms present in the target language in the target language (TL). The shape varies, but the sense or meaning or message stays the same. Translators are now utilizing algorithms to convert one language into another, but humans also play a significant role in determining the final production. Computers do not substitute human beings when interpreting images/metaphors and emotive gestures into literary documents. In a dictionary, translating is more than just looking up a few terms. In company and office contact, we are expected to use English and one of our mother tongues every day to interact with individuals. So, by necessity, we are bilingual and use translation as a way to connect. It is by translation that people interact with each other in the periphery and the middle, the powerful and the dominated cultures. We can claim that without translation, India would not have become a country as we use translation to connect and communication holds us together as a nation.

1. TRANSLATION NATURE

An interpretative method is translation. The quality of the translation depends on the document's nature. It is simpler to translate a scientific or advertising paper which needs less expertise and experience than to translate a text of literature. The terminology, the grammatical laws, and the constructs of the sentence must fit the context of the text, the language of the source, and the target audience. A good translation addresses the target audience's expectations, either in terms of suitable mechanisms or types, or in terms of the appropriate transition of context from the source text to the target text. A successful translator should also have a flair for writing in the target language and be acquainted with the socio-cultural sense in which a text is placed, while possessing equivalent skills in the source language and the target language. No mechanical translator of a document is a good translator. She/he puts to the utmost degree his/her imagination and goes through the soul of the material. As a co-creator of the target language document, we can imagine him/her as the interpreted text that he almost recreates, representing his culture and personality.

2. TRANSLATIONS APPLICATION

Translation was known to be a sub-branch of linguistics in the early days. It has steadily expanded into an interdisciplinary area of research. Translation Research began to work as an independent research unit in the last three decades of the 20th century. The reach of translation today, in this era of globalization, is enormous. In our everyday life, the meaning and importance of translation is multidimensional and extensive. Translation allows one to consider trends in the

areas of performing arts, education, writing, industry, research and politics. Translation has been so important in the post-modern world that it is visualized by citizens as a socio-cultural bridge between cultures and countries. The value of connecting and staying associated with the citizens in other socio-cultural groups is now felt by people, both in their own countries and in countries across the world. Translation has gained growing significance in this sense and serves human, societal and national needs. Let's take the example of Indian culture. Be it literature, culture, history, politics, economics, whatever we see as Indian, it is a fact only because translation has made it possible for citizens to comprehend, view and compile the literature, culture, history, politics and economics of the respective states.

Increasing translation needs and implementations in diverse industries such as colleges, publishing houses, study organizations performing market studies, medical science, travel, culture, public relations and mass communication, foreign organizations, embassies, diplomatic agencies, BPO's, translation and interpretation services are now being provided by several organizations. Junior Translators, Senior Translators, Topic Experts and Assistant Director are needed by all government ministries including External Relations (MEA), Agriculture, Science & Technology, Textile and Education and so on (for official languages). Opportunities for language experts are also offered by private companies such as HP, Oracle, Samsung, Hyundai, LG, Thomson, GE and Aventis, etc. Provided you have the consistency and competence to perform successful work on schedule, the possibilities are infinite. In the immediate future, localization is set to be a multi-billion dollar market. So there would be no greater time than this to begin a translation career. The following areas of translation are more beneficial as required time:

Area of Translation

Literal translation: The first stage of translation is literal translation, where we literally move terms from one language to another. When we want the reader in the target language to grasp the general context of the text in the source language, we typically use this form of translation.

Literary translation: One of the most common forms of translation is literary translation, since it allows world literature accessible in regional languages and introduces literature to viewers around the world in regional languages. Many organizations have opportunities for literary translation at the state, national and foreign level.

Knowledge Translation: Launched by the National Information Committee, the National

Translation Mission supports ventures to translate textbooks and classical works into Indian languages in fields such as sociology, culture, geography, geology, medicine, chemistry, physics, mathematics, linguistics and political science in order to increase the level of education in the Indian language.

Media Translation: With the mushrooming of the print, electronic, visual and audio media industries, newspapers, magazines, radio, television, cinema, internet-enabled entertainment facilities, particularly in regional languages, there has been an increasing need for translators from one language into another. Publishing journals and newspapers and operating TV channels in both local and national languages has been an interesting and lucrative sector and provides numerous jobs and participation opportunities. Translators are now active in the film industry to carry the movies to the masses in many languages by dubbing and subtitling.

Computer-Aided Translation (CAT): Computer-Aided Translation (CAT) methods are constantly being utilized by individuals around the world to address the global market's demands and challenges. In all walks of life, the invasion of the Internet has increased the role of translation in everyday life and has significantly encouraged the usage of computer translation. It is almost difficult, though, to assume that robots can fully substitute human translators.

3. CONCLUSION

Translation is not a word-by-word document translation from one language to another; it brings a text's soul into another's form. It is prudent for you to look at the works of popular translators before beginning translation as a job, to have an understanding of the degree of originality and imagination needed to make a piece of translation look natural and skilled. Before beginning the translation of some work, it is important that a novice in the field of translation should understand the skills of translation. We can eventually switch to nuanced and complicated documents, such as literature masterpieces and information texts in different sciences, beginning from ordinary subjects or technological subjects with less complexity. Similarly, you can switch from tiny roles to broad tasks and initiatives so that you can begin to sharpen the expertise to fulfil the employer's needs, higher the penetration, the better the performance rate. We tackled globalization and the growing function of language, numerous fields of translation such as literal translation, literary translation, translation of information, translation of media and computer translation, increasing role of translation and interpretation and work prospects in translation and interpretation.

REFERENCES

- Bassnett, Susan. (2002): Translation studies. London: Routledge.
- Cronin, Michael. (2003). Translation and globalization. London: Routledge.
- Holmes, James S. (1988): The Name and Nature of Translation Studies. In Holmes, J.S., Translated! Papers on Literary Translation and Translation Studies. Amsterdam: Munday, Jeremy (ed.) (2007): Translation as Intervention. London: Continuum.
- Nida, Eugene A. (1964). Toward a science of translating: With special reference to principles and procedures involved in Bible translating. Leiden: Brill. (p.11)
- Rodopi, 67-80. Reprinted e.g. in Venuti, L. (ed.) (2000), The Translation Studies Reader. London: Routledge, 172-185.

